

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

Electronic Supplementary Information Case Study
PSDI Report

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Project Details

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Project Description

This case study was undertaken as part of Pathfinder 3 to demonstrate how value can be elicited from legacy datasets and to capture the lessons that we can learn from these exercises, both in terms of re-using these techniques on future datasets, but also to help us consider how to store share and archive our current datasets to protect against these issues in the future.

Project Data & Materials

All of the relevant code and JSON files produced as part of this work can be found in our : [PSDI Datasets GitHub Repository](#).

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1 Introduction

In scientific publication, large amounts of data are frequently included via electronic supplementary information (ESI). ESI may take several forms, but frequently consists of PDF files. While the intentions on the part of researchers and authors providing data via ESI are overwhelmingly good, this form of data sharing comes with significant limitations. This impacts re-usability as PDFs are not machine-readable. The requirement to place data in PDF format for publication limits the need to place data in a machine-readable format where the data is reusable for computational analysis. These challenges may be viewed through the lens of FAIR data sharing principles of making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable [1], which ESI frequently falls short of.

There are many scientific experiments in which the published output values do not tell the full story. Raw data gathered from scientific instruments, together with graphical outputs covering a wider range of experiments beyond those reported on directly, can in some cases be more valuable than individual output points. Unfortunately, graphical outputs are often stored as images within supplementary information in PDF format, making them less accessible to humans and machines alike.

Published data in general has the disadvantage of already having been analysed and processed by researchers to be in a format for publications, for example as electronic supplementary information. These formats are often presented in a way which do not lend themselves to data analysis or data reuse, as methods based on machine interpretation such as programmatic approaches will not work without machine readability. In addition, information may be lost between the research and publication phases. The amount of data stored within a publication's ESI is itself a trade-off between the volume of raw data from the scientific instrument necessary to reproduce the final data point and the computational resource needed to host the data. From the perspective of computational resources, storing the entirety of the raw data may be less appealing than storing the processed data. In this case, however, the recording of the process used to analyse the raw data points is essential to ensure that the final outputs are reproducible.

This report will outline the process of extracting data points and graphs from supplementary information about Critical Micelle Concentration (CMC) data. For the purposes of this case study, the paper 'Towards the Prediction of Antimicrobial Efficacy for Hydrogen-Bonded, Self-Associating Amphiphiles' [2] was selected as an exemplar. This paper concerns antibiotic development, a particularly important topic at present due to rise of antimicrobial resistance to existing antibiotics [3] [4] and a recent decrease in the rate of approval of new antibiotics [5]. This is therefore an area in which data sharing and re-usability is especially important.

2 Methodology

To gain an understanding of how the data is currently being used, a review of data was performed on a University of Kent project focused on developing new and novel antibiotics known as self-associating amphiphiles (SSAs). These antibiotics self-associate via supramolecular interactions to form nanostructures, which in turn gives many of these SSAs their antimicrobial activity. This review found that the processing and analysis of data were very results-focused, which caused the analysis leading to the creation of human readable ESI for publication not to be recorded in detail as it is not needed for reproducibility.

While the current ESI approach is inherently very readable to humans, it does not lend itself to future data analysis and reuse. One way to improve on this would be to take the information stored within the plots and figures and make them machine-readable for the data analyst. The data contained within figures and graphs can be stored in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format to achieve this. By storing the data points and definitions of axis labels contained within the graph, this data becomes usable to analysts unfamiliar with the field of the data. The extra

data can be used in separate domain specific analysis or used to provide more information to the models rather than a single processed data point.

For the purposes of this case study, the chosen focus was to develop a method to convert Surface Tension (mN/m) vs Concentration (mM) scatter plots from the paper [2] into a machine-readable format. Figure 1 is an example of the type of graph we aimed to convert into the JSON format.

Figure 1: A figure that shows the Surface Tension (mN/m) vs Concentration (mM)” scatter plot from the supplementary information of the paper ‘Towards the Prediction of Antimicrobial Efficacy for Hydrogen Bonded, Self-Associating Amphiphiles’ [2] used to generate the CMC final data points. This is for the compound where molecule id = 15

The first step was to extract all the images from PDF format into JPGs labeled by their caption within the ESI. This was a 2-step process: 1) extract images (graphs, images, and table), and 2) extract captions. Both proved challenging tasks.

For image extraction, both online tools and Python scripts were trialed to see how accurate they were. However, some of the images could not be extracted from the PDF due to them being copied as an Excel graph format rather than JPGs in the original Word document used to generate the ESI PDF.

For caption extraction, a first attempt was made using PDF text extraction in Python, via the package `pdfplumber` and others. This was unsuccessful because this Python script could not extract the captions, because they were not set as captions when the document was made. The strategy adopted instead was to use an online tool from PDF2GO [6] to convert the PDF to text. This generated line breaks between figures, rather than the block of text generated by our attempts using Python scripts. This was important as the captions within the document did not have an exact/consistent ending condition throughout the document, making it impossible to use regular expression matching to identify break locations. The captions did, however, consistently begin with ”Figure S” throughout. PDF2GO extracted figures along with two blank lines after each one, facilitating the generation of a Python script that added each caption (from ”Figure S” to blank line) to a list.

An unfortunate result of these image extraction issues was that the script generated more captions than there were images. This meant that the captions could not be used to automatically name all of the images. To combat this, the images were instead manually extracted and named. This process was performed on all of the Surface Tension (mN/m) vs Concentration (mM) scatter plots used to calculate CMC, with the hope that information such as the pre- and post-CMC fits could be used to predict the antimicrobial effectiveness of these compounds.

The data points were extracted from the JPG of the graphs using an online tool [7]. The tool facilitates the calibration of the X and Y axes and then select all the data points on the

plot, which returns a list of coordinates. This data was stored in dictionaries in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file, a way of representing structured data in a standard text-based format. Finally, the pre-CMC and post-CMC curves given on the graph were added manually, in addition to the value of surface tension at the CMC associated with the plot, which was stored in a JSON format.

Existing ontologies were searched for key terms used within the custom JSON that was created. Entries for Solvent, Concentration, and SMILES were found using the tool Ontobee [8], but it was not possible to find definitions for CMC itself or for the specific regions of the scatter plot (pre-CMC and post-CMC regions). Although the custom JSONs will work and enable the extraction of information about specific molecules using their `compound_id` and SMILES, the absence of pre-existing definitions does emphasise the difficulty in standardising data and terminology for computational analysis across different studies and different groups.

3 Results

Following the methods described above, it was possible to convert scatter plots of Surface Tension (mN/m) vs. Concentration (mM) into a machine-readable JSON format. An example of this JSON for the graph in Figure 1 is shown in Appendix 1.

To show how storing the data in a JSON format can be of benefit, Python has been used to replicate the Surface Tension (mN/m) vs. Concentration (mM) scatter plot from the supplementary information (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Replication of the Surface Tension (mN/m) vs Concentration (mM) scatter plot from the supplementary information

Concentration (mM)	Surface Tension (mN/m)
95.02	32.20
90.04	31.46
79.94	31.29
69.99	31.29
60.03	30.47
49.93	30.75
40.11	30.64
29.88	30.41
24.90	31.97
22.54	32.27
14.94	34.17
12.45	34.98
9.96	36.47
7.47	37.05
4.98	37.46
2.49	38.98
0.83	39.32

Table 1: Surface tension data for compound 15 extracted using the online data extraction tool.

The scikit-learn library was then used to replicate the line of best fit used to calculate CMC values (Figure 3). This shows how storing a small amount of data (rather than a large amount of raw data) can be sufficient for a lot of flexibility in analysis; and correctly recording this process can allow for both the data and the experiment to be reusable. These results are very similar to pre and post CMC lines of best fit we extracted directly from the supplementary information. [2]

Figure 3: A figure that shows how the data stored within a JSON format can be reused to create figures and re-run analysis from the supplementary information

Type	Slope	Intercept	R-squared
Pre-CMC	-0.3178	39.455	0.982
Post-CMC	0.0231	29.587	0.786

Table 2: Line of best fit parameters from the ESI.

Figure 4 is an example of the raw data, where the mean of each ST (surface tension) in a column at each concentration is used as a data point to plot a graph. Storing this extra data will require increased computational resources without adding notable value to reanalysis of the data.

Figure 4: A figure that shows the raw data used to obtain the final CMC data point. Note this data and plot is for $molecule_d = 40$

4 Conclusions & Future Work

The common practice of archiving data alongside publications via ESI in a PDF format can negatively impact re-usability, as PDFs are not a machine-readable format and raw data from experimental analysis are often only ‘available on request.’ In addition, some potentially valuable data can be lost because the ESI only contains published, often positive, results. The requirement to have data in PDF format for publication limits the need to place data in a machine-readable format, such that the data is reusable for computational analysis. Within

this report, we have shown a method of storing graphs as JSON and the advantages this can bring, although the flexibility of these formats means standards would need to be created and used for each type of experiment to allow for analysis to be carried out on experimental data from multiple groups. It would also be necessary to make the creation of JSON files easily accessible and time-efficient for researchers to avoid any double work. We do anticipate that the JSON files associated with CMC final data points that we have created for this project will be useful in themselves for computational modelling going forward.

In parallel to the work described here, we also worked with the Hiscock group in Kent on handling both published and active data from ongoing research, in particular focusing on CMC data from the paper "Towards the Prediction of Antimicrobial Efficacy for Hydrogen Bonded, Self-Associating Amphiphiles" [9]. A key finding from this work was that there is a drive by researchers to get the data into a machine-readable format, which would reduce the time taken to create the ESI necessary for publication. In addition, storing the data in such a format would simplify data processing and enable the potential advantages that analysis (such as by machine learning) can bring. Given the current realities of scientific publication, however, it is nonetheless important to consider how data can be extracted from existing ESI; the methods for published data that is described in this report are therefore likely to remain relevant.

To reuse data in future studies or replicate experimental results, it is also important to have information about data collection, experimental conditions and sample preparation, collectively known as metadata. An example of this can be seen by considering two research groups measuring the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for some sets of molecules. MIC is the lowest concentration of a substance, under defined *in vitro* conditions, that prevents a specified percentage of bacterial growth within a defined period of time compared to a control [10]. These two datasets could be used in conjunction if the conditions are identical. However, if differences in conditions when measuring the same descriptor exist between the groups, the results may not be directly comparable. Metadata is also important when different variants of the same descriptor have been measured, for example differing percentages of bacterial growth in MIC. This case study's work with the Hiscock group also focused on the recording and storage of metadata in a machine-readable way, but the ESI extraction work does not consider metadata specifically. Future research could investigate the extraction of metadata from existing ESI, and could be integrated with previous work on machine-readable metadata.

5 Outputs, Data & Software Links

The following files have been made available via our [PSDI Datasets GitHub Repository](#).

- **towards_supplementary_info_cmc.pdf** - This is the relevant ESI information that was used for this case study
- **Images and JSON Folder:** This is split into folders for each molecule represented in the ESI Information represented in `towards_supplementary_info_cmc.pdf` - taken from the overall ESI information from the paper *Towards the Prediction of Antimicrobial Efficacy for Hydrogen Bonded, Self-Associating Amphiphiles* (<https://doi.org/10.1002/cmdc.202000533>). Each folder is named for the molecule ID. These folders contain:
 - The original images of the Surface Tension vs concentration plot used to calculate critical micelle concentrate (CMC)
 - The JSON that was extracted from the ESI information. These files contain information on the molecule, its identifiers, the coordinates extracted from the plot and the original line of best fit from the ESI. The JSON file was extracted using methods outlined in the report (insert report info before publication) with definition referenced to

anthologies where the terms are available, see `ontology_references_and_definitions.csv` file.

- **metadata.json & ontology_references_and_definitions.csv** - Machine Readable metadata file in JSON-LD and the relevant ontology definitions that were used in this
- **cmc_json_exporation.ipynb & json_generation.ipynb** - These are the .ipynb files that were used to curate and re-plot the JSON files.

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Appendix 1 - CMC Graph JSON

The full JSON file generated to store information contained within the Surface Tension (mN/m) vs. Concentration (mM) scatter plot from the supplementary information [2] (Figure 2).

Below shows the full JSON file used to recreate the CMC graphs

```
{
  "caption": "Calculation of CMC (28.95 mM) for compound 15 in an EtOH: H2O
  1:19 mixture using surface tension measurements.",
  "compound": {
    "name": "compound 15",
    "SMILES": "[O-]S(=O)(=O)CNC(=S)NC1=CC=C(C=C1)C(F)(F)F.C1=CC=[NH+]C=C1"
  },
  "solvent": {
    "name": "EtOH: H2O 1:19",
    "ratio": "1:19"
  },
  "CMC_value": {
    "CMC (mM)": "28.95",
    "Surface Tension at CMC (mN/m)": "30.25"
  },
  "data": [
    {
      "x": 95.02,
      "y": 32.20
    },
    {
      "x": 90.04,
      "y": 31.46
    },
    {
      "x": 79.94,
      "y": 31.29
    },
    {
      "x": 69.99,
      "y": 31.29
    },
    {
      "x": 60.03,
      "y": 30.47
    },
    {
      "x": 49.93,
      "y": 30.75
    },
    {
      "x": 40.11,
      "y": 30.64
    },
    {
      "x": 29.88,
```

```

    "y": 30.41
  },
  {
    "x": 24.90,
    "y": 31.97
  },
  {
    "x": 22.54,
    "y": 32.27
  },
  {
    "x": 14.94,
    "y": 34.17
  },
  {
    "x": 12.45,
    "y": 34.98
  },
  {
    "x": 9.96,
    "y": 36.47
  },
  {
    "x": 7.47,
    "y": 37.05
  },
  {
    "x": 4.98,
    "y": 37.46
  },
  {
    "x": 2.49,
    "y": 38.98
  },
  {
    "x": 0.83,
    "y": 39.32
  }
],
"line_of_best_fit": [
  {
    "slope": -0.3178,
    "y_intercept": 39.455,
    "R_squared": 0.982,
    "type": "pre-CMC",
    "x_function": "x"
  },
  {
    "slope": 0.0231,
    "y_intercept": 29.587,
    "R_squared": 0.786,

```

```
    "type": "post-CMC",
    "x_function": "x"
  }
],
"units": {
  "x": "Concentration (mM)",
  "y": "Surface Tension (mN/m)"
}
}
```